

A Preliminary Study of the Morphology and Spatial Distribution of Funerary Monuments in the Southwestern Cemetery of Wadi al-Ma'awel, Oman

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Abstract

This study presents a comprehensive spatial and computational analysis of the funerary landscape in the Southwestern Cemetery of Wadi al-Ma'awel, Oman, focusing on tombs from the Wadi Suq (c. 2000–1300 BCE) and Iron Age (c. 1300–300 BCE) periods. Employing an interdisciplinary methodology integrating fieldwork, GIS, spatial statistics, and machine learning, the research examines the morphology and spatial distribution of funerary structures, including Circular, Rectangular, and Ogival types. Results reveal strong positive spatial autocorrelation, indicating non-random clustering of graves by size, likely reflecting cultural or social practices. Cluster analyses identified distinct burial groups, suggesting cemetery segmentation tied to social stratification or familial lineages. The Random Forest model, enhanced by spatial features, achieved improved accuracy in tomb classification, outperforming baseline geometric analyses. The study underscores the utility of computational methods in uncovering latent spatial patterns and social dynamics in funerary contexts, while highlighting the need for richer datasets to improve classification of minority tomb types. These findings contribute to broader discussions on the interplay between funerary practices, collective memory, and socio-economic transitions in ancient southeastern Arabia.

1. Introduction

In the Omani archaeological context, the “Land of Magan”, as designated in Sumerian sources, has been investigated by several international archaeological missions (Fig. 1). Within this framework, the Sapienza Archaeological Mission in the Arabian Peninsula and Gulf has developed research aimed at documenting architectural and spatial transformations in mortuary practice across the Bronze Age–Iron Age sequence, including changes in tomb morphology and construction logic and, in some contexts, the reuse of earlier monuments (Magee 2014; Döpper 2015; Döpper 2023). This paper contributes to this research by presenting an in-depth spatial archaeological study of a diverse funerary context mostly dating to the Wadi Suq (c. 2000–1300 BCE) and Iron Age (c. 1300–300 BCE) periods, examining tomb morphology and spatial organization in the broader context of socio-economic change in southeastern Arabia (Magee 2014).

Figure 1: Map of Oman showing the locations of major archaeological and territorial survey projects, with the MASPAG project area highlighted in relation to contemporaneous research initiatives.

The Southeastern Cemetery in Wadi al-Ma'awel (Al-Batinah South Governorate) (Fig. 2) provides valuable insights into funerary practices in communities that, from the Early Bronze Age onward, developed increasing social and economic complexity; expressed, for example, in more structured settlement systems, intensified exchange networks, and formalized mortuary traditions; from the Early Bronze Age through to the Iron Age (Magee 2014; Chevalier et al. 2016; Döpfer 2023). The site's position between the coastal zone and the Al Jabal Al Akhdar mountain formations makes it a key setting for exploring spatial dynamics and interactions between mobile and more settled lifeways, including the relationship between maritime-oriented communities and pastoral groups within the same regional landscape (Magee 2014).

Figure 2: *Regional context map showing the project area in Oman, its proximity to the Sea of Oman, and its latitudinal position just south of the Tropic of Cancer.*

1.1 Archaeological Context: Funerary Morphology

The study focuses on understanding the evolution of funerary structures in Wadi al-Ma'awel, examining how these graves reflect broader social and cultural changes in tomb morphology or construction. The Southeastern Cemetery contains funerary contexts from various chronological phases dating to the transition between the Bronze Age and Iron Age.

Tombs dated to the Wadi Suq Period (2000–1300 BCE) mark the transitional phase between the Bronze Age and the Iron Age in southeastern Arabia. These above-ground structures, consisting of concentric stone wall tombs, are less monumental than the Umm an-Nar structures, reflecting a shift towards simpler and more practical burial practices.

For the Early Iron Age Tombs a significant gap often exists in documentation between the end of the Wadi Suq period and the Late Iron Age in the Sultanate of Oman. Evidence attests to the reuse of earlier tombs, such as Umm an-Nar structures, in the Early Iron Age, as evidenced by excavations at Bat (Döpfer 2015; Döpfer 2023). Other instances present the possible identification of a discrete category of 'hut tombs' in central Oman. While some scholars identify this as a distinct Late Iron Age cultural entity (Yule 2014; Magee 2007; Magee 2014), others view it as a descriptive label for a group of small-scale

cairn-like graves without clear cultural separation (Deadman 2012). These instances where Early Iron Age burials can be attested do not present a clear morphology. Therefore, the context of the Southeastern Cemetery in Wadi al-Ma'awel serves as an ideal case study to determine if a clearer morphology for funerary contexts from this period can be identified. Likewise, hut-graves in proximity to mining landscapes have been proposed as Iron Age features (Yule 2001; Yule 2014), but the causal relationship between metallurgy and mortuary practice is still debated (Döpfer 2023).

To address these gaps, this study aims to investigate the socio-spatial organization of the Southeastern Cemetery in Wadi al-Ma'awel. Specifically, this research asks: (1) Do the funerary monuments exhibit non-random spatial patterning based on their morphology and dimensions? (2) Can distinct clusters of tombs be identified, and what might they represent in social terms? (3) To what extent can a supervised machine learning model, Random Forest, classify tomb types using geometric data, and does the inclusion of spatial context improve its performance?

Figure 3: *Spatial distribution and typological classification of tombs in the Southwestern Cemetery (Cemetery 185). The map, produced by the MASPAG project, quantifies tomb morphologies, with circular forms being the most prevalent.*

2. Methodology

To investigate whether tomb morphology and spatial organization reflect structured patterns within the cemetery, the study combines field-based measurements with GIS-based mapping and quantitative spatial analyses. Spatial statistics and a supervised classification test are used to evaluate clustering tendencies and to assess whether tomb classes can be distinguished using measurable attributes and spatial-context descriptors.

To this end, this research integrates fieldwork, remote sensing analysis, and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) to investigate the spatial distribution of funerary elements within the context of Wadi al-Ma'awel. In this initial phase, spatial anomalies were mapped using Mergin Maps software, followed by detailed analysis conducted in QGIS, aimed at classifying and categorizing the recorded funerary structures based on geometry and chronology.

The primary study area corresponds to a specific topographic unit (TU2), namely the Southeastern Cemetery, where 185 funerary structures were recorded, including Circular, Rectangular, and Ogival shapes (Fig. 4). The study moves towards a statistical and computational analysis of the collected data. Initially, field measurements are processed using an R script designed to identify correlations and clustering patterns among funerary structures. The primary goal is to illuminate cemetery spatial logic, uncovering patterns that might otherwise remain undetected, thereby revealing patterns potentially indicative of social, environmental, or temporal structuring principles.

Figure 4: *Close aerial perspective of a dense concentration of ogival-like tombs in a defined portion of the Wadi al Mawil southeastern cemetery, highlighting their construction and proximity.*

2.1 Spatial Statistics: R

The use of spatial statistics allows researchers to explore in depth the underlying patterns of spatial distribution, supported by robust mathematical evidence, thus providing a strong scientific approach to the study of space.

Given the inherently spatial nature of archaeological data, spatial statistics has become a prominent approach in archaeological research, particularly in the field of Landscape Archaeology. The latter concept is where this study finds a comprehensive framework as it tries to understand spatial patterns in a landscape that has experienced human activity from the Bronze Age until modern times. For this particular context, spatial autocorrelation, cluster analysis, and hotspot analysis were performed to identify underlying patterns in the cemetery layout. For the spatial statistics analysis, all 185 features were manually verified and measured, then processed in the R Studio environment following the logic: General Statistics, Spatial Autocorrelation, Clustering Analysis, and finally Hotspot Analysis (Moraga 2023; Ripley 2001).

To ensure clarity and reproducibility, key methods are defined here. The Elbow Method provides a data-driven choice of the number of clusters (k) by plotting the within-cluster sum of squares against k ; the 'elbow point' indicates where adding more clusters yields diminishing returns. The Silhouette Method measures how similar an object is to its own cluster compared to other clusters (values range from -1 to 1) (Fig. 5). DBSCAN (Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise) identifies clusters based on point density, distinguishing core points, border points, and noise (outliers), making it effective for identifying arbitrary cluster shapes. G_i^* Hotspot Analysis identifies statistically significant spatial clusters of high values (hotspots) and low values (coldspots) using Z-scores, with values above 1.96 typically indicating significant hotspots.

Figure 5: *Optimal cluster number determination for tomb spatial analysis. (A) Silhouette method confirms k=4 yields best cluster separation for the 185 funerary features. (B) Elbow method identifies k=4 as optimal based on WCSS reduction rate.*

The first step was to examine the spatial autocorrelation of the different points within the dataset. Spatial autocorrelation assesses a variable in relation to its spatial location and observational units; to this degree, it measures the level and strength of the interdependence among the points of a given dataset (Oyana 2020). There are different levels of spatial correlation where values that are relatively close and/or adjacent are usually described as having positive spatial autocorrelation, whereas those that are separate and dissimilar tend to be depicted as negative spatial autocorrelation. In this manner, we aim to see if a primary variable is significant and if its position is significantly dependent on the same variable in other nearby positions (Oyana 2020).

To assess the spatial autocorrelation of these features with focus on Diameter and Length as the main variables, a Moran's I test and Geary's C test were performed on the dataset (Getis 2009). Moran's I was selected as it provides a global measure of spatial autocorrelation, revealing whether tombs of similar size are clustered, dispersed, or randomly distributed across the entire cemetery. Geary's C was selected to complement Moran's I by providing a more sensitive measure of local spatial variation. Where Moran's I test identifies global clustering patterns, Geary's C is better suited for detecting differences between neighboring tombs, making it particularly useful for identifying abrupt changes or boundaries between burial areas that may reflect distinct social or chronological phases within the cemetery.

With the output of these tests ready, the study moved to cluster analysis. Before the development of the code for K-means and DBSCAN, two previous tests—the Elbow Method and the Silhouette Method—were employed to determine the proper number of clusters for the subsequent clustering analysis.

By studying K-means and DBSCAN of the dataset, general patterns of the logic behind the underlying placement and distribution of funerary elements across the landscape that could mirror a social practice and/or distribution could be uncovered (Aggarwal 2018; Madhulatha 2012; Rujasiri and Chomtee 2009). K-means clustering is a method for unsupervised classification that is used to partition the dataset into K distinct clusters, commonly used for spatial pattern recognition. Two diagnostic procedures were used to **select an appropriate** number of clusters for the dataset. K-means clustering was employed alongside DBSCAN to provide complementary perspectives on cemetery organization. While DBSCAN identifies dense, arbitrarily shaped clusters and isolates outliers, K-means partitions the entire dataset into a specified number of groups, ensuring that every tomb is assigned to a cluster. This comprehensive assignment is valuable for detecting broad segmentation patterns across the entire cemetery, even in areas of lower density that DBSCAN might classify as noise.

The final phase of the study handled the analysis of hotspots present within the dataset (Songchitruksa and Zeng 2010). The hotspot statistic is a tool for spatial analysis that identifies clusters of high or low values in a geographic dataset and helps identify areas where graves of similar dimensions are significantly concentrated. The aim of this study was to identify areas of hotspots and coldspots of the dataset to identify areas of great concentration of funerary elements. The G_i^* statistics was employed to identify statistically significant hotspots and coldspots within the cemetery, areas where tombs with high or low dimensions cluster more intensely than would be expected by chance. This method was chosen because it not only confirms the presence of clustering but also pinpoints the specific locations of the most significant concentrations, highlighting potential focal areas for elite burials, ancestral veneration, or other specialized funerary practices.

The application of spatial statistics to archaeological datasets such as this one finds its theoretical foundation in the work of scholars like Hodder, Orton, Clarke, and Rood (Clarke 2014; Hodder and Orton 1976; Rood 1982), who demonstrated that point pattern analysis can reveal meaningful relationships between material remains across a landscape. Central to this approach is the premise that the archaeological concept of 'culture' manifests through strong spatial correlations among different traits and distribution patterns, thereby allowing archaeologists to infer underlying forms of social or political organization (Hodder and Orton 1976; Childe and Wailes 1996; Renfrew 1972). It is within this interpretive framework that the spatial statistics methodology was developed and applied to the present dataset, with the goal of identifying patterns that can inform understandings of socio-political dynamics in the funerary landscape of Wadi al-Ma'awel.

2.2 Random Forest: Python

Random Forest was used as a supervised classifier to compare a **geometry-only baseline** (Diameter, Width, Length, Height) with an **extended feature set** that also includes **spatial-context descriptors** derived from the R-based analyses (K-Means and DBSCAN memberships, and local statistics such as G_i^* , l_i , and $Z.l_i$). This comparison evaluates whether spatial context provides information beyond geometry alone, which is relevant where different tomb morphologies partially overlap in size and proportions. The modelling is intended as an **intra-site methodological evaluation** of class separability within a single cemetery and is not designed for broader predictive modelling or transfer to other regions.

The target variable was the recorded tomb typological class (Class). To handle incomplete measurements, **zero values in the dimensional variables were treated as missing** and recoded as NaN, and missing predictors were handled through **median imputation** implemented within a scikit-learn **Pipeline** to ensure consistent preprocessing during model training and evaluation (Pedregosa et al. 2011). Random Forest is an ensemble-of-trees method trained via bootstrap aggregation (bagging) (Breiman 1996; Breiman 2001); here it was configured with **n_estimators = 100**.

Model evaluation used a **stratified 80/20 train–test split** to preserve class proportions in both subsets. Performance was assessed on the held-out test set using **accuracy** and class-wise **precision, recall, and F1-score**, supported by confusion matrices; given the pronounced class imbalance, interpretation emphasizes precision/recall-based metrics alongside accuracy (Saito & Rehmsmeier 2015). Comparative performance of the geometry-only baseline and the extended model is reported in the Results section (Section 3.4–3.5).

Implementation details (data ingestion/merging, column harmonization, plotting routines, and file I/O) are provided in **Supplementary Material S1** and in the accompanying Python script.

In addition to predictive performance, the Results section reports interpretability and robustness diagnostics, including covariate correlation, permutation importance, and repeated stratified split stability.

Further implementation details for the Random Forest workflow are provided in Supplementary Material S1.

3. Results

3.1 Spatial Autocorrelation: Moran's I and Geary's C Test

The Moran's I test in the Southeastern Cemetery focused on Diameter and Length, as they had the highest data population. The Moran's I results for Diameter (0.2178) and Length (0.2160), both with p-value of 0.0001, indicate strong positive spatial

autocorrelation, suggesting that graves with similar dimensions are clustered rather than randomly distributed.

The significant p-value (0.0001) further suggests a deliberate, systematic placement of graves. In the scatter plot for Diameter (Fig. 6), values closely follow the red regression line, confirming strong positive spatial autocorrelation. Most points fall within the High-High quadrant (top-right), indicating clustering of high values, or the Low-Low quadrant (bottom-left), indicating clustering of low values. Few outliers in the Low-High and High-Low quadrants suggest isolated high or low values. These findings reinforce the structured spatial pattern and highlight distinct zones for future excavation.

Figure 6: *Moran Scatterplot showing the high spatial autocorrelation within the dataset, demonstrating that most values were highly significant to the study.*

Moreover, Geary's C values were 0.681 for Diameter and 0.828 for Length, both below the threshold of 1, confirming local clustering of graves by similar size and reinforcing non-random placement. The scatter plot (Fig. 7) illustrates spatial autocorrelation strength, with low values indicating low spatial correlation and higher variability located at plot edges, highlighting transition points. Higher values indicate greater spatial correlation and clusters of similar graves, suggesting continuity. Most values range between 0.25 and 0.75, indicating general homogeneity but with abrupt local changes. This supports the hypothesis of cemetery segmentation reflecting varying burial traditions, social stratification, or tribal identities.

Figure 7: *Scatter plot of the results of the Geary's C test, showing a strong spatial association between tombs of similar dimensions.*

3.2 Clustering Analysis: K-Means and DBSCAN

The Elbow Method identifies the point of diminishing returns in within-cluster variance, where adding further clusters yields only marginal improvement in cluster compactness. The second test employed was the Silhouette Method to measure the quality of the clusters by assessing how well each point fits within the assigned cluster compared to other clusters.

The K-means results suggest that the clusters are well separated and compact.

In the Southeastern Cemetery, four distinct clusters of varying size were identified (Fig. 8), suggesting meaningful spatial grouping of the graves.

- Cluster 1 (39 graves) – Smaller group, possibly indicating a special burial area (e.g., high-status individuals, unique burial customs).
- Cluster 2 (59 graves) – Medium-sized group, possibly representing standard burials for a particular social class or family lineage.
- Cluster 3 (73 graves) – The largest cluster, indicating a common burial pattern or a densely occupied section of the cemetery.
- Cluster 4 (14 graves) – The smallest cluster, possibly an outlier group or a separate burial tradition.

K-Means Clustering

Figure 8: Plot showing the cluster distribution in a PCA-reduced space, representing the clear segmentation of the cemetery and the assignment of certain features to one of the four identified clusters. Axes represent principal components explaining the majority of variance.

Furthermore, DBSCAN (Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise) detected three major clusters with some outlier values that did not fit the overarching burial pattern of the cemetery. Because this algorithm identifies clusters based on density, it can help identify arbitrary shapes and distinguish noise. The results showcase a dominant cluster that suggests that the points of the dataset are spatially dependent and form a continuous structure. As this test is based on density, it is helpful to identify noise points that are isolated and do not belong to the identified clusters; these noise points could be secondary

features that are near the main cluster but not close enough to be part of it (Fig. 9). This cemetery has two outlier points. Considering the homogeneous results produced by the test, there are no particular regions of anomalies, but rather a cohesive, singular high-density region. The scatter plot indicates that in the main cluster, the tombs might be grouped in pairs, suggesting a strong spatial association among individual funerary elements. Moreover, the linear orientation of the points could be attributed mainly to environmental or geographical constraints.

Figure 9: Scatter plot showing the results of the DBSCAN analysis, highlighting the noise or outlier features of the Southeastern Cemetery.

3.3 Hotspot Analysis

Hotspot analysis identified statistically significant clusters of both high and low values (Fig. 10). Hotspots, with Z-scores ranging from 1.9 to 3.326, can be classified as strong, moderate, or weak

The hotspots, which are those that oscillate between Z-values of 1.9 to 3.326, can be classified as strong, moderate, or weak. The cluster areas that present the strongest hotspots are the central area of the cemetery with a Z-score of 3.3, while the North and East sections display moderate hotspot values with Z-scores between 2.4 and 2.8, demonstrating numeric differences between the hotspots present.

The coldspots also provide valuable insights into the spatial patterns. In the dataset, coldspots are not as prevalent and are mostly located in the southern and western parts of the cemetery. The Z-score values oscillate between -2.58 and -1.9, indicating strong and moderate coldspots. These values indicate clustering of smaller graves, while the hotspots indicate the presence of the largest graves in terms of dimensions.

Figure 10: *Hotspot Analysis scatter plot of the Southeastern Cemetery showing the high concentration of tombs in the center and the isolated tombs at the periphery or edges of the cemetery.*

3.4 Random Forest: Results

The results from the Random Forest model (Breiman 2001)—based solely on the original geometric features (Diameter, Width, Length, Height)—provide a baseline to evaluate classification performance in a context marked by significant class imbalance. Key findings include: Class-wise precision, recall, and F1-score for both Random Forest models are summarized in Fig. 11 (a: geometry-only baseline; b: extended model including spatial-context descriptors).

Fig. 11. Classification metrics for the Random Forest models: (a) geometry-only baseline; (b) merged-input model including spatial-context descriptors.

3.4.1 Baseline performance and error structure

The geometry-only Random Forest provides a baseline for assessing how much typological information is contained in geometry alone. Using a stratified 80/20 train–test split, the model achieves an overall accuracy of approximately 59%, but class-specific performance is uneven and strongly influenced by class imbalance. In particular, the Circular class is classified with substantially higher precision/recall than minority classes, while rare classes (e.g., Irregular) are not reliably recognized due to extremely low sample size. The confusion matrix confirms a tendency to assign ambiguous or minority cases to the dominant Circular class, consistent with the observed class distribution and overlapping geometric ranges among morphotypes.

To avoid over-interpreting a single split, model robustness was evaluated via 50 repeated stratified 80/20 splits (different random seeds). Summary performance metrics (mean \pm SD) are reported in **Table 1**, showing that aggregate accuracy and weighted-F1 remain relatively stable across repetitions, while balanced accuracy and macro-F1 emphasize the limited separability of minority classes under geometry-only predictors.

Predictor	Perm. importance (main split)	Perm. importance (50 splits mean \pm SD)
Diameter	0.141 \pm 0.069	0.074 \pm 0.059

Width	~0 (or slightly neg.)	0.052 ± 0.048
Length	~0 (or slightly neg.)	0.043 ± 0.050
Height	0.011 ± 0.005	0.007 ± 0.008

Table 1. Performance and robustness of the geometry-only Random Forest model (Diameter, Width, Length, Height). Metrics are reported for the main stratified 80/20 split and as mean ± SD over 50 repeated stratified 80/20 splits (different random seeds): Accuracy, Balanced Accuracy, Macro-F1, and Weighted-F1..

3.4.2 Covariate correlation, variable importance, and stability

Given that geometric measurements can be interdependent, Pearson correlations were computed among geometric predictors to assess collinearity and support cautious interpretation of covariate effects; the main correlation coefficients are summarized in **Table 2**. Correlations involving Height with Width/Length could not be robustly estimated due to insufficient pairwise valid observations (missing Height values). Because collinearity can redistribute importance across correlated variables and complicate interpretation of impurity-based importance measures, permutation importance was used for model interpretability.

Permutation importance was computed on the held-out test set using macro-F1 scoring. In the main split, Diameter is the dominant predictor, while Height contributes marginally; Width and Length show lower and less stable contributions, consistent with redundancy among predictors and class imbalance rather than indicating a true negative effect. Table 2 summarizes (a) Pearson correlations among geometric predictors and (b) permutation-importance statistics (mean ± SD) across repeated splits.

Finally, Random Forest does not perform explicit feature selection; rather, it considers a random subset of predictors at each split (`max_features`, default = \sqrt{p}). For the geometry-only baseline ($p = 4$), two predictors are evaluated per split, which contributes to variance reduction but does not remove collinearity-related interpretability issues—hence the emphasis on permutation-based interpretability and repeated-split stability.

Pair	Pearson r
Diameter-Length	-0.70
Width-Length	0.61
Diameter-Height	0.50
Diameter-Width	0.21

Table 2. Collinearity and interpretability diagnostics for the geometry-only Random Forest. Pearson correlation coefficients among geometric predictors (pairwise complete observations) and permutation importance (macro-F1 decrease) computed on held-out test sets, reported for the main split and as mean ± SD over 50 repeated stratified 80/20 splits

3.5 Merged Input: Results

Using the Random Forest implementation in scikit-learn (Pedregosa et al. 2011), we evaluated an extended model that adds spatial descriptors (K-Means cluster, DBSCAN cluster, G_i^* , l_i , $Z.l_i$) derived from the R-based analyses to the geometric measurements. In the main stratified 80/20 split, overall accuracy increased from ~59% (geometry-only baseline) to ~75.7% (extended model). The extended feature set adds spatial-context information not contained in geometry alone: cluster memberships summarize neighbourhood structure, while hotspot scores (G_i^*) and local autocorrelation statistics capture local concentration and similarity patterns. In a funerary landscape where different morphologies may overlap in size and proportions, these spatial descriptors can help separate classes that are geometrically similar but embedded in different spatial settings within the cemetery. Accordingly, the observed improvement is interpreted as support for the usefulness of spatial context for this classification task in the present dataset.

To assess robustness beyond a single split, performance was evaluated over 50 repeated stratified 80/20 splits (different random seeds). Across repetitions, the extended model shows consistent performance (mean \pm SD): Accuracy = **0.797 \pm 0.048**, Balanced Accuracy = **0.517 \pm 0.100**, Macro-F1 = **0.506 \pm 0.095**, and Weighted-F1 = **0.783 \pm 0.050**, supporting the interpretation that the improvement is not driven by a favourable partition.

Permutation importance computed on held-out test sets indicates that the most influential predictors in the extended model are predominantly spatial-context variables (notably G_i^* , $Z.l_i$, and cluster memberships), whereas geometric variables show lower or more redundant contributions under collinearity, consistent with the interpretive role of spatial context within this cemetery.

Class-specific metrics (Circular, Irregular, Ogival, Rectangular, and Squared). Detailed results include: Circular shows excellent performance (F1-score = 0.90), achieving 100% recall and >80% precision. Irregular remains unrecognized (precision and recall = 0.00); because this class is represented by a single instance, it cannot be reliably evaluated in the current train–test setting and requires additional data for assessment. The confusion matrix provides further insight into predictions (Fig. 12a–b): all 23 Circular instances are correctly classified; the single Irregular instance is misclassified as Circular; of 7 Ogival cases, 3 are correctly classified and 4 misclassified as Circular; among 4 Rectangular instances, only 1 is correctly identified and 3 are misclassified as Ogival; two Squared entities split, with one correct and one misclassified as Rectangular. This distribution indicates class overlap (Ogival–Rectangular, Squared–Rectangular) and frequent assignment of Irregular to more common forms, reflecting similarity among features or inherent class imbalance.

Fig. 12. Confusion matrices for the Random Forest models: (a) geometry-only baseline; (b) merged-input model including spatial-context descriptors.

4. Interpretation

4.1 Archaeological Interpretation

The results produced by the computational approaches offer a useful basis for identifying underlying patterns in the spatial distribution of funerary monuments based on their dimensions. These patterns potentially embody cultural ideas and serve as indicators of traditional social practices.

As noted in the results, the cemetery's topography, transitioning from a northern crest to an open southern plain, may partially explain some spatial variation, particularly the greater variability observed in tomb Length (Geary's $C = 0.828$). However, the non-random clustering of tombs by size and the identification of four distinct burial groups suggest that social factors operated in tandem with environmental constraints. Communities did not simply place tombs wherever topography allowed; they organized them according to meaningful principles that persisted across generations.

The spatial autocorrelation results reveal structured patterns possibly influenced by cultural burial practices, social organization, or environmental constraints. Local clustering based on grave dimensions may reflect group burial traditions, family relationships, or social class distinctions. Furthermore, the identification of four spatially distinct burial clusters, supported by the silhouette and elbow methods, suggests clear segmentation within the cemetery itself. The significant cluster sum of squares of 94.1 indicates strong separation among the four identified clusters, reinforcing that the burials most likely followed an underlying spatial organization. The central area exhibits the highest statistical significance in the hotspot analysis (Z-scores up to 3.326), making it a priority for future archaeological investigation. Meanwhile, the presence of coldspots in the peripheral areas of the cemetery, as identified through hotspot analysis, aligns with the

topographic constraints noted earlier. This center-periphery pattern further highlights cemetery segmentation and identifies specific zones for further exploration.

Building on the spatial patterns identified in the results, we now consider their possible social meanings. The clustering of tombs by similar dimensions could reflect a social logic shaped by factors such as social class, ranking, or kinship, behind the spatial patterns.

While the initial research questions focused on identifying spatial patterns, the results invite broader interpretive frameworks. The concept of collective memory, particularly when considered through the lens of geological anchoring, offers one such framework for understanding why these patterns took the form they did. The four spatially distinct clusters may represent what Döpfer (2023) describes as "communities of memory" – groups who maintained shared burial spaces to reinforce social cohesion and ancestral ties. The strong separation between clusters (sum of squares = 94.1) suggests these were not arbitrary divisions but intentionally maintained boundaries. Here, the geological permanence of the landscape becomes significant: prominent topographical features, the northern crest, the stable central zone, provided enduring anchors for collective memory. Unlike wooden structures or portable markers, stone tombs built upon geologically stable formations could transmit meaning across centuries, their physical permanence mirroring the social permanence of the lineages they commemorated.

The concentration of statistically significant hotspots in the central cemetery area is particularly suggestive of this anchoring process. This central zone may have functioned as what can be termed a founder's zone, a designated area where the earliest or most socially prominent individuals of a community were interred, establishing a spatial nucleus around which subsequent generations oriented their own burials. In lineage-based societies, proximity to founding ancestors often served to legitimize kinship claims, reinforce social status, and physically enact connection to collective origins (Saxe 1970; Bloch 1971; Goldstein 1981). The geological stability of this central area made it an ideal location for establishing such a founder's zone, where early or high-status tombs could serve as fixed points for ancestral veneration across generations. The repeated return to this space, evidenced by the dense clustering of tombs around it, suggests that community members actively maintained and transmitted the memory of these founders through the very act of burying their dead in proximity to them.

This interpretation aligns with Lefebvre's (1991) concept of "representational space"—an area imbued with symbolic meaning through repeated use and ritual practice. The central founder's zone, anchored in geologically permanent features, became a landscape of memory where social identity was continuously reaffirmed. In contrast, the peripheral coldspots, located in areas of greater topographic constraint (the southern plain), may have been less suitable for long-term memorialization precisely because they lacked the same visual prominence or geological permanence. These areas may represent later expansions of the cemetery or burial grounds for individuals or groups with weaker claims to ancestral proximity.

Because memory is dependent on diverse variables, it is not fixed and can be flexible, creating multiple meanings (Lefebvre 1991). As such, memory is always constructed by groups of people who can deliberately alter collective memory in response to social or political circumstances (Döpfer 2023). Understanding spatial distribution as a manifestation of collective memory, anchored in both social practice and permanent landscape features, offers a productive way to interpret the social and political circumstances under which these tombs were constructed.

These findings can be contextualized within broader regional patterns. For example, similar spatial segmentation has been observed in cemeteries at Bat and Al-Ayn (Döpfer 2023; Chevalier et al. 2016), suggesting that organized use of funerary space may be a wider phenomenon in Bronze and Iron Age southeastern Arabia.

4.2 Random Forest: Overall Interpretation

- The baseline Random Forest results suggest that, when relying solely on geometric measures, the model primarily classifies the dominant Circular class. Low performance for minority classes is likely due to class imbalance, a common issue in supervised classification (Japkowicz and Stephen 2002). In this baseline setting, geometric features alone capture relevant but insufficient information to discriminate diverse tomb typologies, resulting in only moderate accuracy (59.5%) and limited predictive capability for underrepresented classes. The repeated-split evaluation further indicates that this baseline behaviour is stable and not driven by a single favourable train–test partition.
- When spatial-context descriptors derived from the R-based analyses are incorporated, performance improves in this dataset, with high recall for Circular (1.00) indicating that the combined dimensional and spatial features are informative for characterizing Circular structures. Robustness checks based on repeated stratified splits confirm that the improvement is consistent across partitions. Permutation-importance patterns additionally suggest that the extended model is driven mainly by spatial-context variables (e.g., G_i^* , Z_i , and cluster memberships), supporting the interpretive role of within-cemetery spatial structure for distinguishing morphotypes that partially overlap in size. However, the lack of recognition for Irregular (precision and recall = 0.00) should be interpreted primarily as a data limitation, because this class is represented by only one instance and cannot be reliably evaluated in a train–test setting. Confusion between Ogival and Rectangular classes, and the misclassification of Squared as Rectangular, further suggest overlap in geometric and spatial attributes—an expected challenge with closely related morphological typologies (Ortiz et al. 2013). Overall, these results support the usefulness of integrating spatial and contextual features to improve differentiation among tomb types, while also highlighting the need for richer and better-balanced datasets to assess minority or atypical classes more robustly (Verhagen, Joyce, and Groenhuijzen 2019).

5. Conclusion

The results of this preliminary study demonstrate the significant potential of integrating spatial statistics with traditional archaeological surveys to analyze funerary landscapes. The approach successfully identified non-random spatial patterning and meaningful clusters within the Southeastern Cemetery of Wadi al-Ma'awel, suggesting an organized use of space likely linked to social structure or collective memory.

Several important limitations should be noted. The typological categories established here are based on surface morphology and spatial distribution alone. Their chronological significance remains hypothetical without excavation data (stratigraphy, artifacts, absolute dates) for validation. Owing to the potential homogeneity of surface-visible architecture, any chronological variation within the cemetery remains unclear prior to excavation.

In conclusion, incorporating spatial indicators—including K-means and DBSCAN clustering, G_i^* hotspots, and local Moran's I —successfully reveals underlying organizational principles within the cemetery. The supervised classification experiment further supports the value of spatial context for intra-site morpho-typological separability, and robustness checks indicate that the observed improvement is not driven by a single favourable train–test split. This study illustrates a methodological approach for identifying spatial and social patterns in funerary contexts. However, class heterogeneity and dataset characteristics highlight the need for richer and better-balanced datasets, as well as integration with traditional archaeological methods. Future work should focus on targeted excavation to ground these spatial patterns in material culture and absolute chronology, ultimately contributing to a more robust understanding of funerary practices and socio-economic transitions in ancient southeastern Arabia.

Supplementary material

Supplementary Material S1 provides additional implementation details for the Random Forest workflow (data preprocessing, evaluation, and robustness/interpretability diagnostics). The associated Python script is available in the Zenodo repository (see Code availability).

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Conflict of interest

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Supplementary Materials:

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